

RAMONES

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Disclaimer

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RAMONES project's main objective is to close the current marine radioactivity under-sampling gap and foster new interdisciplinary research in ocean ecosystems. RAMONES will invest a significant effort to provide tools to enable long-term data acquisition missions, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, and propose new AI and Robotics-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. All these may be achieved by combining state-of-the-art (SoA) methodologies and equipment from various disciplines in a well-balanced synergy and designing new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. RAMONES will additionally contribute to shaping a blueprint on Environmental Intelligence in the EU and worldwide.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
AUG	Autonomous Underwater Glider
ASV	Autonomous Surface Vehicle
ROS	Robot Operating System
CSAC	Chip-Scale Atomic Clock
USBL	UltraShort BaseLine
BSD	BackSeat Driver
CAN	Controller Area Network
HITL	Hardware-In-The-Loop
CPS	Counts Per Second

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Abstract

A network of tightly integrated computational systems and vehicle assets was developed to bring to fruition the innovative RAMONES concept of autonomous adaptive radioactivity monitoring in ocean ecosystems. For RAMONES missions, the assets to consider are the fixed benthic station, the two underwater gliders, the autonomous surface vehicle, acting as the main communications hub in the network, and a mission control station, located either on shore or on a crewed surface vessel. Each of the assets is equipped with a computational unit running the software algorithms for the vehicle's navigation and control, the inter-asset communications, data processing and data-flow management, and logging of the radioactivity sensor measurements.

The autonomous underwater glider (AUG) vehicle's navigation solution developed within RAMONES integrates an advanced positioning system based on ultra-short baseline (USBL) acoustic devices, providing accurate position measurements for precise radioactivity mapping and source localization. In typical glider operations it is not possible to adapt mission parameters based on navigation data and sensor measurements as the mission needs to be defined a priori. For RAMONES, the AUGs have been extended with a backseat driver (BSD) option, allowing not only the onboard RAMONES computational unit to access AUG internal parameters and state but, more importantly, to provide reference commands for actuation and modify mission parameters.

The autonomous surface vehicle (ASV) acts as the main communications hub in the network, providing a high-bandwidth communication link between the underwater assets and the mission control station. It is equipped with a more powerful, AI capable computational unit running the software algorithms for the vehicle's navigation and control, the inter-asset communications, data processing and data-flow management, and logging of the radioactivity sensor measurements. For the RAMONES integration and considering the ASV's maneuverability, a new maneuver was designed to allow the ASV to remain near the horizontal position of the underwater assets, thus ensuring a reliable communication link, but simultaneously avoiding sailing against the wind, a maneuver which is difficult for the sailboat to perform in adverse sea state conditions.

The RAMONES system aggregates all vehicle assets and provides an interface to conduct autonomous cooperative missions. A protocol was devised to allow the vehicles to coordinate to perform a RAMONES mission with an arbitrary number of underwater vehicles. The protocol and coordination algorithms for the path following were tested in realistic simulations and in actual marine environments.

Finally, the proposed integrated RAMONES system was demonstrated and validated in operational conditions. A cooperative mission that includes the surface vehicle and two underwater vehicles was conducted, including a full-fledged RAMONES AUG. The vehicles map a region of interest, following dynamically designed paths, and acquire gamma radioactivity measurements through the gamma spectrometer sensors. The RAMONES system exploits the AUGs BSD capability for guidance and control, being able to perform cooperative path following.

1. Introduction

This report presents the final state of the RAMONES work on the integration of the Navigation, Motion Planning and Control, Positioning and Communication systems in a cohesive, flexible, and easily extensible software system and its respective validation using state of the art hardware-in-the-loop (HITL) simulations and experimental field tests.

The proposed software system is a crucial enabler of the RAMONES vision of monitoring ocean radiation through the cooperation of two Autonomous Underwater Gliders (AUG), an Autonomous Surface Vehicle (ASV), and a Benthic Station, towards the critical tasks of underwater localization and relaying of different data streams to other vehicles, as well as benthic and shore stations.

The RAMONES software system builds on the foundational Medusa and NetMarSys software stacks, developed at IST-ID throughout years of operation and simulation of cooperative heterogeneous marine robots. Within WP2, these software packages were refactored to simplify the simulation and operation of multiple vehicles (which can now be done using a single computer). The guiding principles of the refactor were simplicity of use and configuration, modularity of the ROS nodes, and extensibility of the integrated system. This software overhaul was a fundamental steppingstone for the development of the integrated RAMONES system.

Moreover, the software system has been expanded with additional modules to support the RAMONES vision. A module has been created to allow the AUGs to be guided by the onboard RAMONES computer, based on real-time radiation measurements, thereby achieving optimal adaptive sampling. The active guidance is performed using the so-called Backseat Driver feature of the selected AUGs. New functionalities regarding mission management and multiple vehicle communication and coordination have also been developed to achieve the challenging and demanding RAMONES goals.

This final report concludes with a presentation of the completed engineering field trials showcasing the RAMONES system with its cooperative motion control and navigation capabilities. Therein, a system of three vehicles, one surface vehicle and two underwater vehicles, autonomously perform a RAMONES mission of mapping the gamma radioactivity on a section of a water body. The vehicles include a RAMONES AUG and two other ones, acting as surrogates for the RAMONES ASV and a second RAMONES AUG (as not all RAMONES vehicles were available at the time of the tests). This was done without making any changes to the communications, navigation, and control systems embodied in the RAMONES system developed during this project. The ease with which the vehicles can be replaced attests to the modularity and generalizability of the RAMONES system, which uses standard computer components and properly defined interfaces implemented in ROS.

2. AUG Backseat Driver

During the design phase of the RAMONES project, two options for AUGs were available. Both operated as traditional underwater gliders, moving at the expense of an efficient buoyancy engine and lateral fins that generate lift force as the glider moves up-and-down the water column in a yo-yo pattern. Moreover, AUG missions are autonomous and *pre-planned*, meaning that they can only be modified as the glider surfaces and obtains a radio communication link.

The Slocum Glider G3 was selected AUG for the RAMONES project for three main reasons that distinguish it from the competition:

- It can be equipped with an auxiliary thruster and use it for maneuvers where it needs to keep a constant depth.
- The dry payload area could be extended for integrating the USBL/Modem.
- The Slocum Glider G3 can be equipped with a special firmware, the so-called *Backseat Driver* by the manufacturer, that allows the glider to be monitored and commanded in real-time, during a mission.

For the RAMONES project it is essential that the AUGs react in real-time to gamma sensor measurements and the ability of the Slocum Glider G3 manufacturer to provide that feature was a deciding factor.

The manufacturer-provided BSD interface can be used to read and write up to 64 variables of the glider, which are specified through a configuration file on the glider flight computer, named `extctl.ini`. The BSD communication occurs through a serial port in the glider's science bay, which connects the glider's science computer with the RAMONES computer onboard the glider. For ease of integration with the remainder of the RAMONES system, a ROS node was developed to handle the BSD communication and simplify the BSD configuration process. The ROS node is based on open-source code available at [https://gitlab.com/sentinel-aug/ros/slocum_glider] with heavy tweaks to work with the RAMONES computer system and provide a bridge to all the data variables and mission parameters necessary for a RAMONES mission. These include

Input sensors (and units):

```
m_present_time timestamp
m_lat lat
m_lon lon
m_gps_lat lat
m_gps_lon lon
m_depth m
m_roll rad
m_pitch rad
m_heading rad
m_hdg_rate rad/s
m_fin rad
```

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```
m_battpos in
m_de_oil_vol cc
m_water_depth m
m_altitude m
m_altitude_rate m/s
m_thruster_speed rpm
m_avg_thruster_speed m/s
m_thruster_speed_avg rpm
m_thruster_power watt
m_thruster_current amp
m_depth_rate_avg_final m/s
m_pressure bar
m_bms_emergency_battery_voltage volts
m_bms_main_battery_voltage volts
m_lithium_battery_relative_charge %
m_lithium_battery_status nodim
m_gps_status enum
m_bms_status nodim
c_fin rad
c_heading rad
c_wpt_lat lat
c_wpt_lon lon
c_climb_target_depth m
c_dive_target_depth m
c_thruster_value watt
c_depth m
```

Mission parameters (name and description):

```
u_mission_param_a # top inflection depth
u_mission_param_b # bottom inflection depth
u_mission_param_c # heading value
u_mission_param_d # thruster_value
u_mission_param_e # when_secs
u_mission_param_f # target_depth
u_mission_param_g # sci_wants_surface
```

Note that according to the manufacturer conventions, variables starting with 'm_' are *measured* variables and so will be output from the glider to the RAMONES computer; 'c_' variables correspond to *commanded* variables, which are commands requested by the RAMONES computer to the AUG flight computer.

The RAMONES BSD ROS node was designed to parse the BSD configuration file `extctl.ini` and automatically make available corresponding ROS publishers for output variables and ROS services for input variables and mission parameters. This design choice makes it easy to add and remove variables to be read/written as only the configuration file needs to be changed and all the required subsequent changes are automatic.

For cooperative RAMONES missions, the underwater gliders must map a region of interest provided by the ASV. Two approaches were considered for the maneuvers:

- Perform standard glider yo-yo maneuvers for longitudinal movement, using only the glider’s buoyancy engine, without thruster assistance, delimited by a minimum and maximum depth values;
- Perform glider maneuvers at a constant depth, using the auxiliary thruster to generate longitudinal movement instead of the buoyancy engine.

Both kinds of maneuver allow the glider to map an underwater volume of interest. With yo-yo maneuvers the glider moves continuously in the vertical axis while mapping radioactivity, whereas for the “constant depth” maneuvers the glider first maps a 2D region and then proceeds to another depth, repeating the 2D map at a different depth. The former maneuver has the advantage of repeatability. That is, the glider can be commanded to repeat the same exact path if there is the need to gather more radioactivity data in the same region to improve the analysis. In a yo-yo maneuver, the user can only specify minimum and maximum depths for the glider. It is not possible to specify a given exact depth dependent on the x-y position.

For the AUG motion control trial, the BSD was configured to make use of standard constant depth missions where the thruster is used to propel the AUG while the heading direction, desired depth, and thruster power can be changed programmatically (through the BSD interface). The corresponding files onboard the glider computer and the RAMONES system software running on the RAMONES computer are available to the consortium on a privately shared GitHub repository (<https://github.com/ramones-eu/glider-ramones>). Note that the RAMONES system and the proposed solution are flexible and any behavior that the AUG can perform (constant depth, yo-yo, etc.) can be used as a basis mission if the relevant variables and mission parameters are made available on the BSD interface.

AUG Motion Control Field Trials

The Backseat Driver AUG interface was tested in a realistic simulation environment that allowed to do the initial debugging and parameter tuning, after which the system was ready to be trialed out in the real world with the actual AUG. The selected test location was an artificial lake in Portugal, selected for its proximity to IST-ID headquarters, available facilities for a support vessel, reasonable water depth (around 50m) and large work area.

To assess the AUG BSD and its integration in the RAMONES system, a desired path was defined and the AUG was commanded to follow it at a constant depth. The path following uses the existing outer-loop controllers in the RAMONES system to provide yaw references to the AUG, with the speed being defined through the specification of the thruster power. For the presented trials, the thruster power was 5 W (of a maximum power of 10 W), resulting in an average horizontal speed of 0.35 m/s. The yaw references are continuously computed by the path following algorithm and sent to the AUG flight computer through the BSD interface. The BSD then updates the mission parameter corresponding to the yaw angle to be tracked and follows it using its internal inner-loop controller.

Figures 1 through 5 depict the evolution of the path following maneuver (real data from real trials). The BSD control is evinced in Figure 1, where the glider yaw reference is continuously updated based on the path following guidance loop. The AUG tracks the yaw reference reasonably, remaining within a small region around it throughout the maneuver.

Figure 1 – Glider yaw and its yaw reference.

Figure 2 depicts the cross-track error for the glider path following maneuver. After the initial transient, the cross-track error converges to zero and path following is attained. The glider remains at the commanded constant depth of 6m throughout the path following maneuver. Occasional deviations are seen, which originate in external disturbances, but the glider control loop is engaged and limits the depth errors to a maximum of approximately 1.5 m.

Figure 2 – Glider path following cross-track error.

Figure 3 – Glider actual and reference depth.

Finally, the surge speed remains almost constant and equal to 0.35 m/s during the maneuver (Figure 4). A top view of the glider commanded maneuver, positioning measurements and positioning estimates is presented in Figure 5.

Figure 4 – Glider surge velocity.

Figure 5 – Plot x,y of AUG position measurements, filtered position, and desired path.

3. Sailboat integration in the RAMONES system

The A-TIRMA G3, depicted in RAMONES operations in Figure 6, is ROC-SIANI/ULPGC's autonomous sailboat. It was chosen as the autonomous surface vessel to integrate the overall RAMONES architecture for its long endurance capabilities and environmentally conscious propulsion method. The ASV's main objectives within RAMONES are to move cooperatively with the underwater gliders, provide essential navigation information and serve as a communication relay between the above water Wi-Fi and cellular networks and the underwater acoustic network.

Figure 6 - A-TIRMA sailboat in operations off Gran Canaria, Spain, cooperating and providing navigation information to a glider surrogate vehicle.

The sailboat's native software and hardware, developed by ULPGC's team, provides the ability for a remote system (onboard or offboard) to receive telemetry from the ASV and command it to follow specific routes or maintain a position or course, through existing primitives (e.g. waypoint following, course following, position hold, etc.).

For RAMONES, the sailboat was additionally equipped with a so-called "RAMONES Computer" (more details below) in order to implement the RAMONES system. This computer is connected to the sailboat's onboard Science Computer via a CAN bus, which intermediates the receiving of the sailboat's telemetry and sending commands to the sailboat. For cooperative RAMONES missions, the motion commands were chosen as the most appropriate within the ASV motion primitives and correspond to a set of new waypoints for the sailboat to follow. Additionally, and attending to the sailing characteristics of the sailboat, a particular maneuver was developed to avoid tacking, because the sailboat isn't able to do it in adverse conditions. Details on this maneuver and its afforded advantages are provided in section 7.

Moreover, to be able to communicate with the gliders, an EvoLogics acoustic modem, also with the USBL option, was integrated, ensuring communication with both underwater gliders as well as accurate relative positioning.

The RAMONES Computer on the sailboat consists of a NVIDIA Jetson Nano, running Ubuntu 20.04.5 LTS similarly to the glider's RPi4, and a custom ROS interface was developed in order to bridge ULPGC's and RAMONES' systems, making it possible to send custom routes via the latter. Moreover, vehicle information such as its position, velocity and system health status are also made available, along with current wind speed and direction. A Jetson Nano was preferred for the ASV as it is more powerful than a Raspberry Pi 4, such as the ones installed in the AUGs, and has edge AI capabilities, which are used to process the gamma radiation data and determine the next region of interest to be monitored within a mission. These increased computing capabilities come at the expense of larger power and energy requirements. However, these are not as problematic in the sailboat as for the AUGs, since the sailboat has solar panels and can recharge its batteries during the day-time of a mission.

4. Acoustic Communications

EvoLogics' acoustic modems and USBL play a critical role in the overall architecture of the RAMONES system, since they lay the groundwork for multi-vehicle cooperation and underwater acoustic positioning.

For this purpose, synchronous instant messages were used, which are instant messages with time-triggered transmission that can deliver a payload of up to 64 bytes. For RAMONES a number of AUG and ASV states and radioactivity summary measurements are exchanged within that available payload.

Regarding the interrogation scheme, a silent approach and a pinger/replier approach have both been implemented. In the former configuration, the ASV sends an acoustic pulse at a pre-agreed interval which the AUGs can use, in an inverted-USBL configuration, to determine their accurate underwater position. In the latter configuration, a master/pinger vehicle (in this case, the sailboat) is responsible for alternately sending acoustic messages to both underwater gliders. In addition, these two vehicles are repliers, only transmitting acoustic messages after being interrogated.

The existence of an USBL unit in the glider empowers it with the ability of calculating the bearing and elevation of an acoustic source in the local USBL frame upon receiving a transmission from it. Thus, in a situation where a surface vessel sends its inertial position acoustically to a glider and given the range between the two (which can be easily computed given the speed of sound and the travel time), then the glider can compute its own inertial position, which is essential for its own navigation system.

To improve the AUGs position estimates, the USBL position measurements are fed to a navigation filter which maintains an accurate estimate of the AUG based on its dynamic model and uses the measurements as corrections. For RAMONES, a Kalman filter for the overall AUG state is used, which is able to smooth out USBL position measurements and reject outliers, common underwater due to seabed and sea-surface reflections, in a phenomenon known as multi-path.

Pinger/Replier Communication Architecture

This section describes the architecture of the implemented pinger/replier communication scheme, through the USBL acoustic modems. This communication scheme, used during the Santorini trials, considers the following goals:

- Localisation of the underwater glider vehicle and position visualisation.
- Data transmission from the AUG to the surface through piggyback messages, including gamma measurements and glider navigation and status information.
- Modification of the mission parameters through the BSD commands based on messages sent from the surface.

For the successful communication with the glider vehicle, a custom architecture was developed and implemented considering two acoustic modems: the ASV topside modem and the Glider modem. Dedicated ROS software modules were implemented on the glider vehicle

to handle the message exchange with the surface unit, as well as communication with the underwater glider science computer.

On the topside, several python scripts were implemented for exact position calculation and real-time visualisation on an interactive GIS interface.

The communication scheme was designed and executed using Python and ROS to coordinate the transmission and reception of specific messages via the EvLogics acoustic modems. The following figure illustrates the communication architecture, while implementation details are provided in the next section, detailing the implementation of the ROS stack.

Figure 7: ROS acoustic communications architecture for USBL pinger/replier scheme

Processing Modules

The above architecture is composed of two parts, the surface processing part and the glider processing part. Processing on the surface was implemented through python scripts running on a dedicated computer. These scripts allowed for precise calculation of the glider position, logging of position data and received data from the glider as well as on-screen position visualisation:

- **GNSS_Logger:** Reads NMEA GPS data from a serial port, converts coordinates from WGS84 to the Greek Grid system, and logs timestamped position and altitude data to a file.

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- **USBL_Logger:** Connects to the topside modem, pings the glider modem, processes relative position responses and data responses (including piggyback messages) and continuously logs the extracted data.
- **Position_Calculator:** Monitors GNSS and USBL log files, fuses their data to compute adjusted coordinates and distances, and updates an interactive map.

Data processing on the Glider is done using ROS. Specifically, the following ROS nodes are implemented for Backseat Driver command handling and sensor data transmission to the surface:

- **TCP_TO_ROS Node:** Connects to the glider modem through TCP, listens to incoming instant messages, cleans and publishes relevant commands to the /device_data ROS topic.
- **EXTCTL Node:** Listens to the /device_data ROS topic and forwards relevant commands to the glider backseat driver.
- **Sensor_Publisher Node:** Reads glider status, navigation and sensor data and publishes these to dedicated ROS topics for transmission to the surface.
- **PB_Node:** Piggyback ROS node ingesting glider status, navigation and sensor data and updating the glider modem piggyback buffer for transmission back to the surface.

Position Visualisation

On the surface, both the GNSS position of the surface vehicle as well as the calculated glider position are visualised and shown on an interactive map. Glider-to-Boat distance as well as glider depth are also calculated and shown on the same map. The following figure presents an instance of this visualisation, for a mission in the Kolumbo underwater volcano crater during the operations performed in Santorini on October 26th and 27th.

Figure 8: Screenshot of interactive interface for AUG and ASV visualization during the operations that took place at Kolumbo on October 26th and 27th

Inverted USBL Pinger/Replier Communication Architecture

The main objectives of the inverted USBL pinger/replier solution are achieved through the following main steps:

1. Glider pings the ASV and the benthic lab modem using its USBL device.
2. Current (most recent) GPS coordinates of ASV are transmitted to the glider via piggyback messages.
3. Glider estimates its own global position based on USBL messages produced by the EvoLogics USBL device mounted on the AUG and ASV GNSS coordinates contained in the received piggyback messages.
4. The Glider pings the Benthic Lab modem and initiates burst data transmission when in range of the Benthic Lab.

A communication architecture was developed and implemented considering three (3) acoustic modems: the ASV topside modem, the Glider modem, and the Benthic modem. Dedicated ROS software modules were implemented to handle the message exchange of the modems, as well as communication with the underwater glider science computer.

The communication scheme was designed and executed using ROS to coordinate the transmission and reception of specific messages via the EvoLogics acoustic modems. The following section provides an overview of the ROS stack used to implement the communication framework between the Glider, the Surface Vehicle, and the Benthic Lab.

Figure 9: ROS acoustic communications architecture for inverted USBL pinger/replier scheme

The backbone of the ROS-based communication scheme consists of various ROS nodes and ROS topics. These components enable the required computations and allow for data exchange between devices. ROS nodes act as “processing nodes” that implement the logic for specific calculations, while ROS topics serve as “communication channels” for data exchange between the nodes.

In our implementation, the “top-side” (i.e., the ASV) can control the glider using a set of predefined messages sent to the underwater vehicle’s backseat driver. The “top-side” can also initiate and terminate data collection on the glider, including position calculations, by sending start and stop commands.

Upon receiving a start command from the surface, the glider begins transmitting instant messages (IMs) through the EvoLogics acoustic modem to the acoustic modem on the surface vehicle. The surface vehicle responds with acknowledgement messages that include piggyback data (exploiting the modem’s piggyback message functionality) containing its GNSS coordinates, which are returned to the glider.

Using the received GNSS coordinates of the surface vehicle and its relative position to the surface vehicle, the glider calculates its global position. This position is then retransmitted to the surface for visualization purposes.

The implemented ROS architecture also supports sending command messages from the glider to the benthic lab and receiving burst data when the glider is within range of the lab. It

should be noted that this functionality was only tested in the NTUA lab and not in the field tests.

ROS Nodes

The following list provides a short overview of the different ROS Nodes and Topics of the implemented ROS communication architecture.

- **DC_NODE:** Data Collection Node. This node collects and formats all data to be published on the */data_send* topic. This can include GNSS data, status data etc.
- **PB_NODE:** Piggyback Node. This node subscribes to the */data_send* topic and sends them to the piggyback buffer for transmission with the next acknowledgement message.
- **TCP_TO_ROS:** This node listens to incoming acoustic messages and publishes them to the */device_data* topic.
- **EXTCTL:** This node subscribes to the */device_data* topic and forwards incoming messages to the glider backseat driver. This node also publishes a request initialization message to the */data_req* topic to initialize the inverted USBL pipeline on the glider.
- **DR_NODE:** This node sends request messages to the surface vehicle, collects incoming data and publishes them to the */inc_data* node.
- **CP_NODE:** This node reads the ASV global position as well as its relative position, from the */inc_data* topic and calculates the glider's own global position. The calculated global position is then published to the */data_send* topic for re-transmission to the surface.

Acoustic communications Field Trials

Field experiments for testing positioning and communication involving the EvoLogics acoustic equipment of the benthic lab, the underwater glider and the surface vehicle were successfully completed at the area of Palaia Fokaia, Greece. The location of the expedition, indicated by the green rectangle in Figure 9, was selected for its proximity to the NTUA laboratory, where one of the two RAMONES underwater gliders is located, and its suitability in terms of sufficient depth and easy of access that facilitate experiments with the acoustic devices and the underwater glider.

The tests aimed to address three main objectives, each associated with specific sub-tasks that were verified during the expedition and in the lab:

1. **Test the inverted USBL solution:** This solution enables the underwater glider to determine its position based on an inverted USBL solution, eliminating the need to calculate the position of the underwater glider on the surface and retransmitting the estimated position to the glider, increasing robustness while offering better geolocalization of the data collected on the glider.

2. **Benthic modem acoustic release:** The goal was to test the triggering of the benthic modem's acoustic release at the desired location, allowing the benthic lab to return to the surface.
3. **Transmission of data from the benthic station (using burst mode):** This step focused on ensuring the reliable transmission of bulk data from the benthic station, in burst mode.

Figure 10: Location of experiments in Palaia Fokaia (indicated by the green rectangle)

Inverted USBL pinger/replier solution tests

The inverted USBL pinger/replier USBL solution was successfully tested in the field expedition at Palaia Fokaia. During the tests, two scenarios were considered. In the first, the glider was commanded to perform a small number of yo-yos at four different headings, North, East, South and West. At this time the surface boat, equipped with the GNSS and the top-side USBL, was kept at the same position. The second scenario considered "mooring" the glider at a small depth while the surface boat performed circles around it. The correct estimation of the glider position, as computed on the AUG using the inverted USBL solution, has been verified both via the on-line interactive visualization interface, and via the difference between the estimated location of the glider right before surfacing and the measured GNSS coordinates acquired during surfacing.

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Figure 11: QGIS visualisation of the deployment area showing the surface vehicle and glider position along with the glider's depth

Figure 12: Glider path along S-N direction based on inverted USBL solution from Dec. 17th

Figure 13: Boat path circumnavigating the glider reconstructed based on inverted USBL solution on Dec. 18th

Acoustic release and burst data transmission

The experiments for the benthic modem acoustic release and data transmission from the benthic station were primarily conducted in NTUA's lab. By sending the appropriate command from the topside modem to the benthic station's acoustic modem, we successfully triggered a thermal reaction in the release mechanisms. This reaction caused the release mechanisms to open, enabling the entire station to detach from the flotation device. This was tested for both release mechanisms at the NTUA's pool.

Burst data transmission from the benthic lab was tested as follows. A sample file from the gamma sniffer used in the Santorini trials was stored on the benthic station's acoustic modem, taking the role of the benthic lab's collected science data in a real environment. The acoustic modem of the benthic lab was then set up to listen incoming acoustic messages, expecting a specific command message to be received. Upon successful reception of the command message, sent in our case from the topside modem, the benthic lab's acoustic modem successfully transmitted its data payload through burst mode to the topside modem, making use of the existing data compression filter (i.e. *zlib* libraries).

This capability of transmitting data streams to the ASV and subsequently to a shore station, outside the marine environment, was used to transfer data from several radiation-sensing instruments, such as the previously mentioned γ Sniffer, as well as GASP (high-

resolution HPGe-based instrument) and α SPECT (a prototype radon spectrometer for the marine environment). All radiation sensors relied on the infrastructure developed for the benthic lab to transmit stored information, so as to provide near-real-time information on the environment conditions in which the benthic lab was operating.

Besides single data streams per instrument (e.g. fully digitized spectra) time stamps populated the data stream to provide the capability of correlating the radioactivity data with the operating CTD device and the γ Sniffer, both mounted next to GASPARG and α SPECT.

5. RAMONES mission definition and control

Bearing in mind the cooperation of an Autonomous Surface Vehicle such ULPGC's A-TIRMA sailboat and the two Autonomous Underwater Gliders, it is of pivotal importance that all vehicles are synchronized regarding how and when to communicate with each other acoustically. The following flowchart illustrates the adopted Acoustic Communications protocol.

Figure 14 - Flowchart for the ASV mission initialization.

At the start of a RAMONES mission, the sailboat is in idle mode and its first action is to send an acoustic broadcast message, to which all the listening underwater gliders answer back, sending in the response message's payload their own unique vehicle ID, which is in turn saved in a list of participating vehicles.

Subsequently, when all underwater vehicles intended to participate in the cooperative mission are successfully paired up with the sailboat, it sends the zone of interest to each AUG, characterized by minimum and maximum longitude and latitude values, rotation angle and target depth.

If all participating vehicles acknowledge the new mission's zone of interest, then the sailboat starts its own maneuver, in cooperation with the gliders - otherwise, it sends them a request to abort the mission, and the pairing process restarts with the ASV in idle mode.

At the end of the initialization process, the ASV and all AUG vehicles agree and are synchronized with respect to the maneuver to be executed and which paths are to be followed by each vehicle. A cooperative path-following mission then starts and proceeds until the whole area is mapped, and the system idles again, or an external abort mission signal is received by the RAMONES system.

6. Cooperation and Path Following

The RAMONES cooperative missions typically consist of equally spaced paths, covering the entirety of the zone of interest, to optimize the monitoring capabilities of the overall system.

This coverage can be achieved in two distinct manners, depending on the mission requirements. If the variable to optimize is mission duration, then a simple lawnmower-type maneuver is generated for each vehicle, characterized by straight lines and semicircular turns connecting them, with alternating turn directions. The individual paths of each underwater vehicle are equally separated in space to minimize mapping overlaps (these depend on sensor range) and optimize the mission duration. If due to mission requirements, a revisitation of mapped areas is desirable, then a spring-like lawnmower path is chosen, characterized by straight lines connected by semicircular turns with alternating radii, with constant turn direction. This latter approach is preferable if the sensors are not sensible enough and require longer mapping time than the one afforded by the reference vehicle speed.

Figures 15 and 16 illustrate both cases for multiple vehicles, in the scope of the full RAMONES system.

Figure 15 (left) and 16 (right) - Different lawnmower-like maneuvers, designed to map the radioactivity of a certain area of interest.

Once each vehicle is assigned a specific maneuver, with a corresponding path to follow, inter-vehicle cooperation is achieved by synchronizing each of the vehicle's progressions along its respective path. If the vehicles' progression along the path is identical then they perform a coordinated maneuver. Coordination is achieved through the sharing of each vehicle's progression along the path with the remainder of the vehicles. By comparing an AUG's progression variable with the other vehicles', a surge speed correction term is computed and added to the nominal desired speed for the vehicle, ensuring that ultimately the progression variables converge to the same value, compatible with the desired path progression speed, and all vehicles progress along their paths side by side with the same speed.

The sailboat motion is constrained by the wind speed and direction, and it is crucial that it isn't commanded to follow a waypoint directly against the wind, since it would require tacking several times to move in that direction in a zigzag pattern. Tacking, in nautical terms, refers to the maneuver of turning a sailing vessel's bow through the wind so that the wind

changes from one side of the vessel to the other. This is done to make progress against the wind by combining the motion in two different directions. because the sailboat isn't able to do it in adverse conditions because when going against the waves it loses speed and its rudder loses effectiveness.

Hence, a series of waypoints are issued to the ASV to create a figure of eight path along the original cooperative path (i.e. the figure of eight is centered at the average AUG position), in order to keep it moving even against the wind, ensuring the sailboat never needs to tack (the change of wind side is done by jibing), as seen in the figure below. Jibing (or gybing) is a sailing maneuver where a sailboat turns its stern through the wind, causing the wind to shift from one side of the sail to the other. Looking at Figure 17, which depicts the proposed continuous-looping maneuver, it is clear that at no time the desired heading for the sailboat (purple arrows) faces the forbidden sector of 45 degrees centered on the upwind direction (blue arrow).

Figure 17 - Proposed continuous looping maneuver for the ASV, such that it never faces the wind.

7. Scalable multi-vehicle simulations

The RAMONES system architecture was designed to be fully scalable to any number of vehicles, which allows it to incorporate, manage, and command any reasonable number of physical AUG vehicles. The main limiting factor for the number of vehicles is the number of available acoustic channels and acoustical IDs, which ranges in the hundreds. This scalability is afforded in both the actual system and simulation.

In simulation, there is the additional computational overhead required to simulate every vehicle, including their sensors and actuators, and the environment. This poses limits to the number of vehicles that can be simulated in a single computer in *real time*, as after adding a few vehicles the simulation computer might be overloaded. The distributed nature of ROS, the middleware underpinning the RAMONES system, provides an elegant way to overcome this limitation. A network of computers, each simulating multiple vehicles, can be created and used in a joint simulation of a large swarm of vehicles in a RAMONES mission, providing seemingly infinite scalability without rigid computational limitations. If further computational resources are needed then a new computer can be added to the network for the extra CPU power needed for simulating the new vehicles, instead of being limited to the computational power of a single computer.

A representative simulation of a swarm of 11 vehicles total (1 ASV and 10 AUGs) performing a cooperative RAMONES monitoring mission was implemented. The results are presented in the sequel, starting with Figure 18, depicting the lawnmower paths followed by the vehicles. These are equally spaced and are well tracked by the individual vehicles. The vehicles start the mission at different points along the pre-defined paths.

Figure 18 – Lawnmower paths followed by the swarm of vehicles.

Figure 19 shows the evolution of the progression along the path (γ) for each vehicle. After an initial transient all the progressions converge to the same value, constantly increasing at the same rate. This is further corroborated in Figure 20, where the derivative of the path progression is shown for each vehicle.

Figure 19 – Path progression parameter for each vehicle in the swarm.

Figure 20 – Derivative of the path progression parameter for each vehicle in the swarm.

8. RAMONES system final engineering trials

In order to extensively test the RAMONES system and proposed solutions, a representative scenario was set-up at the artificial lake of the Castelo de Bode dam, Portugal, using a RAMONES architecture of three autonomous vehicles, one surface and two underwater, one of them being an AUG. For practical reasons, and to avoid more logistic costs of transporting the ASV and second AUG to Portugal, two replacements were made:

- The second AUG was replaced by an autonomous underwater vehicle provided by IST-ID - the Medusa Yellow.
- The ROC-SIANI/ULPGC sailboat was replaced by an autonomous surface vehicle provided by IST-ID - the Medusa Black.

The third vehicle was the full-fledged RAMONES glider owned and operated by IST-ID, equipped with a RAMONES gamma sniffer provided by Ploatech, and an acoustic USBL-modem provided by EvoLogics. The standard SLOCUM G3 glider was augmented with an extended section, housing the acoustic modems, extra batteries and the RAMONES computer. This computer runs the RAMONES mission software, operates the gamma sniffer sensor and performs the communication with the Glider Backseat Driver hardware.

For the mission, a lawnmower path was defined, with straight legs 100 m long and an arc with radius of 50 m (for the AUG). The selected nominal speed for these vehicles while performing the path following was 0.35 m/s.

Figure 21 illustrates the desired paths for the three autonomous vehicles and shows, superimposed, the actual vehicle trajectories. It can be seen that after an initial transient, all three vehicles were capable of following the lawnmower path. Furthermore, the formation was coordinated and moving as a whole, as can be attested from Figures 22 and 23, showcasing the progression along the path for each vehicle and its derivative.

Figure 21 - Desired paths and trajectories for the three coordinated vehicles performing a RAMONES maneuver (real data).

Figure 22 - Progression along the path for each of the three vehicles performing a coordinated RAMONES maneuver (real data). Identical progressions along the path correspond to a coordinated maneuver.

Figure 23 - Derivative of the progression along the path for each of the three vehicles performing a coordinated RAMONES maneuver (real data). In a coordinated maneuver, these converge to the same value, as seen above.

Finally, gamma sniffer data was acquired during this mission, proving that the developed system is capable of obtaining geo-referenced radioactivity data and monitoring a certain area, all while cooperating with another AUV and an ASV. The figure below shows measurements of the integrated counts per second (CPS) during a 10-second acquisition interval over the course of the mission. Since there were no close-by radioactivity sources, the measurements are consistent over time and correspond to the natural background radiation.

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Figure 24 - Integrated CPS during a 10 second acquisition interval over the course of a RAMONES mission (real data).